
DETECTING EXTREMISM IN TWEETS USING LEXICON-BASED TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Social media enhances communication across geopolitical boundaries. While it serves as a tool for healthy interactions, it has also been used to propagate disinformation aimed at causing fear, disaffection, and other acts that could lead to physical attacks. This use of computers and the internet to promote such extremist views is considered cyberterrorism. This study proposes an unsupervised learning technique to detect extremism in tweets and identify those who make such posts. A lexicon-based technique was used to compute sentiment scores of tweets, and a rule-based method was applied to categorise them. Experiments were carried out with tweets posted before and after the Kuje prison break of July 2022 in Abuja, Nigeria. Correlation analysis shows that tweet engagements have strong relationships. Also, it was noted that negative tweets tend to spread faster, with extremely negative tweets getting the most engagement, such as likes and retweets. Results from the experiment showed that the framework produced 0.90 accuracy and recall, 0.96 precision, and the F1 score was 0.93. Future studies may consider other machine learning tools and improve accuracy in automatically detecting extremism on Tweets.

Keywords: Twitter, Extremism, Cyberterrorism, Sentiment Analysis, Kuje Prison Break

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Social media, especially Twitter, provides freedom to share information of common interest and network with other users. However, there are incidents where social media has been used to propagate fake news, hate speech, recruitment and radicalisation of vulnerable users to terrorise society. Violent extremists often take advantage of social media to promote their nefarious activities, knowing that their posts could spread remarkably within a short time (Mussiraliyeva et al, 2023; Ekong et al, 2021; Sharif et al., 2019). Detecting extremism in user-generated content, such as tweets, is quite challenging (Mussiraliyeva et al, 2023).

Govers et al (2021) noted that extremism could be politically inclined outside regular social beliefs or tend to support violence. Sentiment analysis of text reveals the emotions or opinions being conveyed (Ejodamen et al, 2023). While sentiments are either positive, negative or neutral, extreme views align with extreme positive or negative boundaries. In particular, violent extremism exhibits highly negative sentiments, which could spread relatively fast if not curtailed (Sharif et al., 2019).

A case study of a terrorist attack was the Kuje jail break, which triggered conversations on Twitter. Kuje Prison – officially called a “Correctional Centre” – is a medium security facility for criminal suspects serving jail terms or awaiting court judgements. It is located at a part of Abuja, Nigeria. The security architecture of the facility was breached on 5th July 2022 by terrorists who freed all prisoners, especially their members awaiting trial (Abeku, 2022). The Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) claimed responsibility for the prison break, which led to the death of some security personnel and significant damage to the prison facility. The news triggered conversations on social media, especially Twitter. While some posts criticised the prison break, others subtly supported it and blamed the government for negligence.

This study proposes a technique to automatically detect terrorism-inclined tweets and their supporters in cyberspace. The objectives include the construction of a dataset of post-terror tweets and designing an unsupervised machine learning framework to detect terrorism supporters. Also, this study identifies which sentiments tend to spread faster.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Mussiraliyeva et al (2023) explored how extremism spreads online, emphasising the need to accurately analyse digital content. Machine learning tools were used to model their system and evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 statistics, producing results up to 85.97%.

Identification of extremism in tweets was the focus of Sharif et al. (2019). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to reduce the dimensionality of tweets before applying machine learning algorithms such as Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), as well as ensemble classification. SVM outperformed others with 84% average accuracy.

Aryuni et al. (2020) proposed an early warning system to detect terrorism in Twitter content posted in the Indonesian national language. The study applied the Naïve Bayes Algorithm with 77% accuracy.

Pano and Kashef (2020) examined various text pre-processing techniques to determine an optimal method for predicting Bitcoin prices using a lexicon-based approach. Another study by Al-Shabi (2020) focused on lexicon-based sentiment analysis of social media text. Models such as VADER, AFINN-111, SentiWordNet, SentiStrength, and Liu and Hu Opinion lexicon were compared. VADER outperformed the others on accuracy, positive and negative recalls, as well as both positive and negative F1-scores.

Oriola (2018) proposed a computational linguistic approach to predict sentiments supporting terrorism by Boko Haram and Niger-Delta militancy. Machine learning algorithms – Naïve Bayes and Decision Tree – were used for modelling, while reporting the same accuracy (77%) for both algorithms when applied to the Boko Haram dataset. However, Decision Tree outperformed Naïve Bayes in the Niger-Delta dataset.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A purposeful sampling technique was applied in mining posts centred on the Kuje prison break using keywords commonly used by terrorists. This technique is non-probabilistic, requiring a sample of the population data needed for the research to be determined by the expert, subject to the set goal (Bhardwaj, 2019). In this case, the data required has to be related to a terrorist activity, such as the Kuje incident. Data was programmatically retrieved, cleaned, manipulated, stored, and classified according to the sentiment of the tweets posted. The proposed

analytic architecture for detecting extremism in post-terror tweets is shown in Figure 1.

3.1 Data Collection

Tweepy – a Twitter Application Programming Interface (API) wrapper developed by Roesslein (2021) and used to gain access to historic tweets about the Kuje prison break. This is made possible with the approved access credentials obtained to enable the researcher to mine tweets from 1st May 2022 and 30th September 2022. The terrorist invasion of the Kuje facility occurred on the 5th July 2022. Hence, two months before and after the attack were chosen to capture as much relevant data as possible. Data downloaded was stored in a Comma Separated Value (CSV) format to enable future manipulations and analysis.

Tweets that met the selection criteria were 8,172 from various accounts. The basic features of the datasets retrieved include Tweet ID, User ID, the date the tweet was posted, the automatically identified language of the tweet, and the text itself. Notably, the Tweet ID is a Twitter autogenerated value that uniquely identifies every tweet posted. It is a nominal data type that may be used to obtain other metadata of the tweet. Similarly, the User ID is an identity assigned to uniquely distinguish between Twitter user accounts. Also, the age of the tweet is calculated as the difference between the date it was posted and the current date.

In addition, users can relate and engage with publicly available tweets. This significantly shows the relevance of a tweet, because people tend to associate with posts that interest them. Twitter provides data on engagement metrics, which are relevant for extracting insights. They include the number of likes, retweets, replies, and quotes.

3.2 Data Pre-processing

A visual and programmatic assessment of the dataset was carried out to check for data quality and tidiness issues. As is common with data from social media, the downloaded tweets had several noisy data such as user mentions, hashtags, stop-words, and so on. Stop-words are words (such as 'the', 'an', 'you' etc.) that do not add any lexical value to a block of text. The presence of stop-words is considered noisy and should be removed. Similarly, other Twitter users could be mentioned in a posted tweet in the form '@username'. For the sentiment analysis of the tweets, user mentions are irrelevant and excluded before lexicon polarity computation. Similarly, hashtags are words preceded with a '#' (e.g #WeCanRead), often used for emphasis about a topic. It is commonly used in social media to help interested

persons find topics and interact with the community. While hashtags may provide some insights, such as trending topics, this research does not consider it in its analysis as the topic is on a particular movie review. Also, web links were in several of the tweets. However, they are irrelevant in this study. Hence, all web links were deleted from tweets.

The language used in social media is dominated by acronyms and slang. The character limitation of Tweets has further encouraged users to find ways of completing their statements within the limits permitted. To achieve this, acronyms are used. It can be observed in Figure 3.3 that "ASAP" is used instead of the full meaning "As Soon As Possible". It is important to replace acronyms, as was also applied by Azzouza (2017), before performing sentiment analysis. This ensures the correct sentiment information is derived, hence improving the quality of the analysis.

In a sentence, it could be used as a past tense, present participle, future tense, and so on. For example, the word 'kill' can be used in communication as 'killed', 'killing', 'killings', e.t.c. The process of normalising or mapping words to their standard form is known as 'stemming' or 'lemmatisation' (Weiss et al., 2015). While stemming simply returns the root word, lemmatisation considers the context when converting the word to a meaningful base form.

Figure 1: Proposed architecture for detecting extremism in tweets

3.3 Sentiment Classification

The lexicon-based technique of this study adopts the VADER model for polarity computation of words in a tweet to determine its overall sentiment polarity. VADER has a corpus of words and sentiment scores assigned to each (Hutto and Gilbert, 2014). These scores were derived from the experts' opinions of each word. The sentiment score of a sentence/document/tweet is a summation of the sentiments of individual words present.

Thereafter, a rule-based technique is applied to classify tweets based on the computed sentiment score. The sentiment class (S) of a tweet, as shown in Eq. (1), is classified as high positive/high negative if the computed sentiment score of the tweet is greater/lesser than 0.7/-0.7, or positive/negative if it is between 0.05/-0.05 and 0.7/-0.7. Plain tweets with negligible sentiment scores between less than minus 0.05 and less than plus 0.05 are classified as neutral. The high negative threshold aims to identify tweets with extreme sentiments.

$$S = \begin{cases} \text{High Positive} & s \geq 0.7 \\ \text{Positive} & 0.05 \leq s \leq 0.7 \\ \text{Neutral} & -0.05 < s < 0.05 \\ \text{Negative} & -0.05 \geq s \geq -0.7 \\ \text{High Negative} & s \leq -0.7 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

4.0 EXPERIMENT AND RESULT ANALYSIS

Sentiment analysis of the data after applying rules shows the dominance of highly negative (44%) tweets in the post-terror discourse. As shown in Figure 2, the negative sentiments were 29%, while 12% posted positive comments and 4% were highly positive.

Figure 2: Sentiments of tweets about the Kuje prison break

However, 11% of the posts during the period surveyed were neutral or having extremist posts, as this has great implications that could result in agitations and physical demonstrations/violence.

4.1 Sentiment Classification by Tweet Engagements

It is worse if the spread of posts with extremist content is high. It is noteworthy that retweets, for example, increase the spread of information. All followers of an account would see the retweet. In Figure 3, it can be noticed that extreme sentiments received more engagements, with quotes being the highest, with 42%. Positive sentiments were the least engaged. This shows the need to curtail extremist posts early enough, since negative tweets tend to go viral faster.

Figure 3: Engagement of tweets by sentiments

Pearson correlation is used in the study to examine the relationship between the tweet's engagement. There is a strong relationship between the number of likes versus retweets (0.88) and likes versus quotes (0.72). However, while the correlation of quotes and replies is very strong (0.90), likes and retweets moderately correlate with replies (0.64). Also, retweet correlates strongly with quotes (0.79).

4.2 Detection of extremists

The user who posts any tweet can be uniquely identified, irrespective of the number. The average sentiment score (earlier computed) for each user is used to identify if the user is a suspected extremist or not. A suspected extremist may be so-called if the average sentiments are below -7.0. It is common for a single account to make multiple posts. Hence, in the experiment, the average sentiments of all the tweets within the period are computed to determine the sentiment score.

This framework was tested on a standard dataset developed by Aldera et al (2021). The dataset contains tweets from verified extremists and non-extremists, which experts labelled. As is common with extremist posts, many of the accounts have been deleted as of the time of mining the tweets. The tweets were

converted from Arabic to English using Google Translate before other steps in the framework. Results from the experiment, when compared with the standard label in the dataset, showed that the framework produced 0.90 accuracy and recall, 0.96 precision, and the F1 score was 0.93.

This finding implies that the lexicon-based technique can also be used to detect extremism in tweets. Such detection will help to minimise the activities of violent extremists to radicalise and promote anti-social narratives. It will also provide security agencies with much-needed data to commence investigations in case it triggers violence.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Extremist content is prevalent in social media posts, especially tweets. This type of negative post, if not detected early, could spread like wildfire, resulting in physical consequences. This study proposes a technique to automatically detect extremists based on sentiments in their tweets and other user features. Each tweet was cleaned to remove undesirable elements such as stopwords and hashtags, then it was tokenised and lemmatised. Thereafter, sentiment analysis was performed using VADER to classify the tweets into positive, neutral, and negative. Detecting violent extremism in tweets requires identifying highly negative sentiments below -0.70 . Where a user account has several posts, an average of the sentiment scores is computed, and an extremely negative sentiment is flagged as suspicious. Analysis of the data showed that negative tweets were more engaged (liked and retweeted). Notably, findings indicate that likes of tweets are highly correlated (0.88) with retweets. Results from the experiment showed that the framework produced 0.90 accuracy and recall, 0.96 precision, and the F1 score was 0.93. This suggests that the framework can reliably detect violent extremism. Future studies may apply machine learning models and compare them with the results from this study.

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